

A Study of AI in Empowering Banking System

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Abstract

Since 1956, Artificial Intelligence has been around as the subfield of Computer Science dedicated to development of programs to enable computers behaving by the ways that can be represented as intelligent. The word artificial intelligence (AI) initially used and coined by John McCarthy and defined as "The science and engineering of making intelligent machines".

Keywords: NLP (Natural Language Processing), Speech Recognition, NLG (Natural Language Generation), Deep Learning, Machine Learning, VR (Visual Recognition)

The development and study of AI has been fascinated and under focused discipline in recent, to date the utilization of AI inevitably raised as an irrefutable truth in different fields that shows its comprehensive nature to shape a new face of world and make the opportunity for humans to most challengeable tasks in future of technologies.

The banking and business domain also has not been quiet from, launching of various processing programs in space of customers led to powering the modern methods of banking and integration of AI as valuable virtual assistant to consumers being exposed by for business and usual solutions.

The use cases of AI constantly changing, but banks are concentrating on three main applications; 1. Building a better customer experience, 2. Reducing costs, 3. Streamlining risk operations, that will be applicable by providing the platforms of using Speech Recognition, Deep Learning, Machine Learning, VR (Visual Recognition), NLP (Natural Language Processing), NLG (Natural Language Generation),

Recently a notable majority of consumers believe AI can reduce the time it takes to get answers tailored to their preferences, as well appreciate to pay a premium for a hybrid AI system that also offers direct access to humans.

Eventually the use of AI besides its great and high performance, gradually challenge the employment rate with tangible change among different job markets. So, this ungovernable progression will be durable or take a stop flag as a risk signal in upcoming future?

Objectives

1. To explore role of AI in progression of banking system.
2. To look into different cases on utilization of AI in progressive banks.
3. To examine influence of developing AI on employment.

Methodology

The present paper under title of Study of AI in empowering banking systems made by collecting relevant data and information that is corresponsive to the discussion of paper and all are based on relevant books, journals, newspapers, statistical facts and case studies that already published.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) developed as a profound functional subfield of computer science and proliferated in various disciplines and operational fields based on its high usage and working. Since AI defined “The science and engineering of making intelligent machines” (John McCarthy, 1959) it made a considerably revolution and development in empowering of processing systems. Banking system is one of the affected and under focused domain of AI that overall had a substantial and helpful progression toward the more efficient services for customers. Basically the banking system in East and Pacific passed its inclusive way and has different methods that can also determine their capacities in acquiring of AI in system of processing and analyzing.

There are three main types of banks: Central banks, Investment banks and Retail banks. Central banks operate in high sort of making decision and managing of monetary system and establishing of a general plan of action for other banks. While it is only the investment and retail banks that are directly in interact with customers and giving services, so of course AI brought banking and industry surmises following definition: “Artificial Intelligence is an area of computer science that emphasizes the creation of intelligent machines that sense, comprehend, reason and act to emulate human behavior.

Some the activities that computers with AI are designed for include image and speech recognition, learning, planning and problem-solving. Example of applied AI technologies include (but are not limited to): machine learning, deep learning, predictive/prescriptive analytics, virtual agent and natural language understanding technologies (Siri, Alexa, Google, Home, Amelia etc.). (Infosys, Finacle, 2017).

AI Building Blocks

For designing and assembling AI systems ten building blocks are essential, often AI simplest use case is consisting of a single building blocks, but in most of times more than one blocks combine together and modified to create a customized application, the building blocks organizes according to either be relevant to data, to processing, or to action.

Data

- Machine vision: Detecting faces and objects in images
- Speech recognition: Transforming spoken words
- Natural language processing: Detecting the intent in a text-based command

Processing

- Information processing: Reasoning by analogy to related concepts
- Learning from data: Learning to drive car from recorded data
- Planning and exploring agents: Building a map while exploring the environment

Action

- Image generation: Modifying faces in a picture
- Speech generation: Providing speech to a virtual assistant
- Handing and control: Picking up novel items
- Navigating and movement: Avoiding obstacles as an autonomous vehicle

The six key technology building blocks for empowering and banking solutions has its popular applications in banking that often they called with their synonyms also and there is briefly a clarification of them.

Popular Applications in Banking

- machine learning: in banking machine learning finds applications so neatly such as customer services, fraud/risk management, personal wealth management. Mostly it can be used to identify fraud or vulnerability of system in its payment.
- Deep learning: by its multitude ways of apply in banking process, it can be used to check fraud by considering typical behavior patterns of user and largely judgment on basis of the amount of transaction. Useful for finding business opportunities as deep learning can help banks access relevant promotions and customer information and behavior on social networks from their preference and wants. For instance, Amazon and Alibaba.
- Natural language processing (NLP): banks are using this to examine and exploring of customer attitude toward the brands and offerings being exposure from social media conversations. NLP can lead to providing faster and more efficient customer service through AI-based digital assistants that ultimately, system would learn customer and agent behavior to settle same issues automatically.
- Speech recognition: help banks to enable more efficient authentication by offering voice option to customers. Besides its ease of use, is a natural correspond for securing payments.
- Natural Language Generation (NLG): mainly used to generating awareness or answer in an understandable form and it has to be assembled from various sources to be responsive for customers. For instance, Amelia.
- Visual recognition: authorize bank customers to pay bills by simply taking a picture using their smart device. Australian bank was the first to allow customers to activate a new card through their smartphone cameras, including several banks like Bank of America, Citibank, Wells Fargo, TD bank etc.

Regarding to application of building blocks, a set of Case study from different banks include of Indian banks that share their experience of utilizing brought here for better grasp.

1. Case example: DBS Bank

Singapore's DBS Bank is using an AI-powered Virtual assistant called KAI to enhance the experience at digibank, its mobile-only bank in India. KAI can understand language the way humans speak it, this will help digibank to reply to thousands of customers queries and in consequence they (customers) can fulfil banking transaction in real-time, anywhere and anytime.

2. Case example: ICICI Bank

India's ICICI Bank has deployed software robotics in more than 500 business processes, covering a million banking=g transactions every day. It is the first bank in India to do so.

The use of software robotics has cut the time taken to respond to customers by 60% and increased accuracy to 100%. The robots, which are working in variety a variety of retail banking operations, as well as in treasury and human resources management among others, capture and interpret information, recognize patterns and run processes to perform functions like data entry and validation, automated formatting, text mining, reconciliation and exchange rate processing etc.

Important areas of AI application

As discussed in before parts, AI has a comprehensive application into several banking process that building blocks are the mediums to cover the various demand and tasks of customers and in consequence, answer their inquiries and wants. The process generally has front, middle and back office levels in glimpse that perform these operations.

1) Front Office

- Customer service
- Sales and marketing
- Wealth advisory and financially assistance

2) Mid Office

- Risk assessment
- Fraud detection/AML
- Credit scoring

3) Back Office

- Settlements processing
- Cash & liquidity management
- Reconciliation

3. Case example: Front office, Swedbank Nina

At Swedbank Group, an intelligent virtual assistant named Nina is rendering conversational customer service to help customers and agents help themselves. Customers type their queries via the website and Nina helps them find answers and also products and services best suited to their needs.

AI and Employment; Since its Emergence & Developing

AI are taking every industry by storm since it arises and make significant role in making tasks and processes better. Most of jobs are going to get automated sooner than we think and this acknowledged by a statement of Elon Mask (CEO & Founder of Tesla & SpaceX) where he said “AI powered system and automation technologies are going to replace most human jobs very soon and all countries may have to adapt universal basic income programs for their citizens to cope with aftereffect of this revolution.” At this time whereas AI need language programmers to create algorithms to automate the processes and it means AI itself create job opportunities to Tech markets but, AI-powered system has the ability to reach a point where becomes able to program itself, again exposure humans in situation to replace their jobs in favor of AI eventually.

For instance, Fukoka mutual life insurance in Japan sated that more than 30 of its employees will be replaced with an AI system. In addition, Fukako mutual life insurance brought in an AI which costed them £1.4m but, the company’s expert say that it would be saving £1m yearly while it need routine and unplanned maintenance that costs about £100k a year as company reported.

Jobs that are Vulnerable to AI Revolution

Based on a widely acclaimed study, there are a set of jobs which are vulnerable to AI revolution, Carl.B Frey & Michael Osborne found out the probability of automation for 702 jobs and led to the result that 47% of employees in America are at higher risk of losing jobs. It warned the employees working in transport and logistics (Taxi drivers and couriers to be replaced by self-driving cars and car pools), security office support staff (security guards and front desk officers to be replaced by computerized check-ins and securities), and sales and customer support staff (cashiers, telemarketers, call-centers assistant, clerks are to be replaced with chatbots and machines). (JOHN BARNETT,2017)

Conclusion

I argued the development of artificial intelligence in domain of banking system and more focused on how facilitate the various banking system processes, in addition to the capacity of banking system that has been able for AI industry and applications. by the end of all progression, Impact and influence of AI on employment that is the main challengeable problem on the way of AI development as by some steps of developing reaches to singularity and somehow anautocracy discussed and obviously understood that approximately for next three decades when the population is expected to reach 9.8 billion people and over 6 billion of them will be working age while we are already struggling with finding decent employment for 71 million young people worldwide.

AI will govern the Tech markets rather than our today perspective toward employees and employment problem.

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